

Biological fouling of water transport vehicles: state, problems, possible solutions

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Abstract

Features are represented of biological fouling of water transport vehicles in the course of their operation in various aqueous basins of the world ocean. The modern state of this problem is shown; the existing and promising work directions are given in frame of the fight against the fouling of the ship underwater parts. The factors are listed influencing the ships fouling intensity. Two directions are pointed out of researches and practical work for this problem overcoming: prevention (reduction) of the biological fouling and cleaning of the ship hulls accumulated the fouling. There are shown the possible methods, ways and means used for the realization of the specified work directions. Based on the considered results of the conducted researches, the proposals are put forward on possible solutions of the ships biological fouling problem.

Keywords: Water transport, Ship, Biological fouling, Methods, Ways, Means, Fouling prevention / reduction.

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1. Introduction

About the problem of the ships biological fouling, the human race is concerned since the ancient times of construction of the first ships. On the initial stage of the shipbuilding, the fouling phenomenon was not being taken seriously. However, with time, this problem started causing significant economic and environmental harm, so the necessity arose of ships cleaning from the fouling resulting in ships operational characteristics worsening and intrusion of alien organisms provoking changes of local dwellers of the aquatic environment because of ships bringing them into the national territorial waters.

As a result of the fouling, the part of the ship hull being submerged into water is covered with a layer of marine plants and animals, which is accompanied with a ship speed reduction, an increase of fuel consumption, the mechanisms fast wear and the operational expenses growth. The intensive fouling is able to cause the ship speed reduction down to two knots an hour and the fuel consumption growth by 40%.

Often at getting into the aqueous environment, where previous parasites and predators are absent, the alien aqueous organisms-foulers propagate in large quantities. Upon that as a result of competition or eating away, they are able to suppress or completely replace the local kinds of organisms, which can result in significant worsening of water quality, propagation of parasites and diseases including ones dangerous for humans.

This paper is aimed at analysis of the problem state of the biological fouling of the water transport (WT) vehicles and proposals putting forward of possible directions of researches and practical works for its overcoming.

2. Development

The ship fouling is a crust (knag) formed on the ship parts submerged into the water as a result of the vital activity of organisms' colonies dwelling in the aqueous environment (bacteria, algae, invertebrates) and the mineral particles build-up. On their sizes, the organisms responsible for the fouling are divided into two categories: microfoulers (bacteria and other unicellular organisms) and macrofoulers (invertebrates and algae). More than 1,700 kinds of the marine organisms can participate in the fouling creating a

local ecosystem [3, 6]. The ship fouling starts with formation of a film of bacteria and unicellular algae on its surface and ends with the phase of stable biocenosis, as it is shown on the illustrations.

Figure 1. Fouling on ship hull ².

Source: [7, 8]

Figure 2. Fouling on boat hull ³.

Source: [9, 10]

² There's a battle brewing underwater. Every year millions of dollars are spent combating bacterial films, called biofilms, that grow relentlessly beneath ships, corroding the structure, clogging undersea sensors, and adding drag that can increase fuel consumption by up to 40 percent. [8]

³ In the fight against marine fouling in the world annually spent \$ 100 billion. So far, there is only one way of protection: paint and varnish with toxic copper compounds are applied to the case below the waterline. Russian scientists have found environmentally friendly compounds that protect against this! [10]

After getting onto a ship hull, those organisms attach to it extremely firmly, so that even the storms in the sea cannot tear them off.

In the biological aspect, this is the natural process making an integral part of the hydrosphere life. Any disturbance of the established equilibrium of the fouling ecosystem as well as that of the benthos can cause unexpected shifts of this balance including extremely undesirable ones.

The studying of the WT vehicles fouling was started as long ago as in 20s of the previous century. The founders of the complex research are considered to be the scientists E. Hentschel from Germany and J. Visscher from USA. In 1923 based on results analysis of fouling of 48 ships, E. Hentschel composed his table of the discovered species in diverse regions of the Atlantic Ocean, where those ships were operated. For each region, he found out the peculiarities of composition and distribution of various forms. In his turn, J. Visscher examined 217 ships affected with the fouling and analyzed the dependence of their fouling extent on conditions of their operation⁴ (Visscher, 1928). The reports on the ships fouling were regularly met in the world scientific literature before 1960s⁵. (Hentschel, 1923; Perry, 1931; Bertelsen, 1936).

In USSR, the detailed researches on ships fouling problem were conducted since 1950s-1960s⁶ (Tarasov, 1959, Zehvina, 1961, Rudyakova, 1958). In particular, this problem was studied quite comprehensively on the White Sea in the Arctic Ocean⁷ (Oshurkov, 1982, Sirenko, 1978). Also the researches were conducted on the Black Sea associated with the Mediterranean Sea⁸. (Brayko, Dolgopolskaya, 1974; Brayko, 1985).

The analysis of the results obtained in these and others similar researches of WT vehicles fouling shows [11, 12] that largely the fouling intensity depends on a region of floating and quality of anti-fouling covers used for protection of a ship hull underwater part. The clamshells are attached to the underwater surfaces by the way of excretion of their binding substance (so called “glue of marine duck”). This substance is produced by lines of coupled glands on a marine clamshell

surface; it hardens in the water for 10-15 minutes. In addition, the intensity of the marine fouling depends on the water temperature; in tropical latitudes, the fouling goes faster. For as short time as half a year, the ship bottom can be covered with the knag up to 7 cm in thickness and by hundred tons in mass, especially if there were long-lasting stops in ports.

For the fight with the fouling, the developed countries spend huge amounts of finance: for these purposes, England allocates £20 million per year; about the same amount in dollar terms is spent by the United States⁹ (Zehvina, 1994).

In operation, because of the biological fouling of the ship hulls, ship owners can practice two interrelated directions of researches and their practical realization, which – by the way – are similar to the ways of the treatment problem of ship wastes [13]: firstly, finding methods of prevention (or reduction) of the fouling and secondly, cleaning the ship hull from the fouling.

At the present time in Russia, the first direction is realized in line with the directive document [14] specifying – in particular – the basic statements and technical requirements on seaborne machinery protection against the fouling, the order of acceptance and control of works on the fouling protection. Notably, it is required that the fouling prevention systems should be installed on both new ships during their construction and operated ships.

Previously, for ship hull protection against the fouling, the applied method prevailed consisting in ship plating with thin sheets of copper. However, it is quite poisonous not only for foulers but also for many useful dwellers of the aqueous environment. The other method consisted in coating of a ship hull with covers containing compounds of mercury, arsenic, tin and copper, which are also toxic for dwellers of the aqueous environment; so such methods were stopped to be used.

For painting of the ship hull, whether it would be its outer parts or the underwater metal surfaces, the paints are used based on the ethanol lacquer. For protecting of ship's area of the variable waterline, covers are used based on polyvinyl chloride, a copolymer of vinyl chloride with vinylidene chloride, phenol-formaldehyde and perchlorvinyl resins. For more reliable protection

⁴ Visscher, (1928).

⁵ Hentschel, (1923); Perry, (1931); Bertelsen, (1936).

⁶ Tarasov, (1959); Zehvina, (1961); Rudyakova, (1958).

⁷ Oshurkov, (1982); Sirenko, (1978).

⁸ Brayko, Dolgopolskaya, (1974); Brayko, (1985).

⁹ Zehvina, (1994).

of the ship underwater parts, the paints are applied able forming water-and corrosion-resistant covers stable to the fouling by the marine organisms.

The most widely accepted agents for painting of the outer ship surfaces were enamels based on pentaphthalic varnish, paints based on polyvinyl chloride, mixtures of perchlorvinyl and alkyd resins as well as copolymers of vinyl chloride with vinyl acetate.

Later on for the fouling prevention, a number of fundamentally different methods were proposed [3, 12, 15]. In particular, the method was developed of the ultrasonic protection by excitation of high frequency vibrations in the ship hull, which prevents the larvae's colonization. A possibility was studied of a gas protection of a ship hull against the fouling by supplying of ship power plant fuel combustion products into the near-wall water layer.

Also for realization of the second direction of the fouling fight, i.e. for ship hulls cleaning from already accumulated fouling crust, a number of methods were developed and applied. For example, the process is used of surfaces cleaning with dry ice pellets (technology of CO₂ granules blasting). The CO₂ granules blasting is the cleaning process, in which the dry ice pellets flow is accelerated by a compressed air jet and sent to the surface to be cleaned.

The underwater ship hull cleaning can be conducted with methods that are more effective. For example, the fouling is removed from the ship surfaces by use of the hydrodynamic cavitation. This method is used, when it is impossible to do it mechanically.

Also there exists the method of the mechanical cleaning with aid of hydraulic metals; it is indispensable in cases of severe fouling and also, when a ship needs to be cleaned very quickly, during a stop or a raid in a port. This method is based on the action of a rotating mechanism equipped with a special brush driven by a hydraulic motor. The so-called brush-cards are able to fulfill cleaning of both horizontal and vertical surfaces and remove virtually all existing kinds of fouling.

3. Conclusions and proposals

Despite of the rather large number of existing methods of ship protection from a biological

fouling, no radical method is found yet able to prevent it completely.

In the practice, chemical fouling protection prevails as the most widespread direction. Nowadays, it is actively developed in many developed countries. It is connected with underwater use of paints and other covers able releasing potent poisons (biocides) that unfortunately kill not only foulers but also any other aquatic animals.

Promising directions for practical overcoming of the problem of WT vehicles biological fouling can be as follows:

- ❖ development of policy frameworks (concepts) in the area of the Russian territorial waters for the protection of WT vehicles from the biological contamination;
- ❖ development of legislative acts and normative documents on prevention and control of ships fouling including the alien species intrusion because of their bringing by ships;
- ❖ creation of national database on fouling species including the pathogenic and alien species of aqueous organisms;
- ❖ arrangement of monitoring of biological diversity in the Russian territorial waters;
- ❖ development of concrete measures on prevention and control of ship fouling intensity, especially as it concerns the WT vehicles' bringing pathogenic and alien species of aqueous organisms in their train into the Russian territorial waters;
- ❖ development of techniques of the biological fouling control and ships cleaning from fouling;
- ❖ development of techniques of treatment and utilization of products of the ships cleaning from the biological fouling.

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